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POST-STROKE DEPRESSION: NEUROCOGNITIVE EVALUATION AND REHABILITATION

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ABSTRACT

Cerebral Vascular Accident (CVA) is a neurological condition considered one of the greatest concerns in public health, due to the significant burden of disability and dependence. In this article, a theoretical review is carried out focused on the signs and symptoms presented in patients in an ischemic process, considering that studies reveal that among the symptoms, post-stroke depression (PAVC) is the most frequent emotional disorder. CVPD has a high prevalence, and despite this, it is poorly detected and treated. Many risk factors and negative repercussions on patient recovery are associated with CVAPD. Thus, knowing the nature and its risk factors becomes essential to improve its diagnosis and treatment, since its study is considered relevant due to the important contribution of neuropsychology in the course of brain disorders, specifically cognitive changes associated with Cerebral Vascular accidents (CVA).) and the relationship between the neuropsychological findings and the presence of depression in these patients, allowing a broader analysis of the need for studies that take into account the relationships between mood and functioning cognitive.

Keywords: Stroke; Depression; Cognitive Assessment; Neuropsychological rehabilitation.

INTRODUCTION

Cerebral Vascular Accident (CVA) is defined as a vascular aggression that causes a lesion in the brain, resulting in neurological deficits. However, the term evolves to include injuries caused by hemodynamic and coagulation disorders, even in the absence of detectable changes in arteries and veins, thus vascular injury must be understood in a broader context of the complex interactions between the vessel (endothelium), figurative elements of the blood and hemodynamic variables (ANDRÉ, 2006).

Stroke is a chronic neurological condition classified as one of the most prevalent diseases worldwide, with 15 million victims each year. Considered one of the most important causes of disability in developed and underdeveloped countries. Being the leading cause of disability in adults in the United States and Canada. Although stroke death rates in North America have shown substantial declines, approximately millions of Americans and 300,000 Canadians are currently living with the effects of stroke. Differences in stroke severity and symptoms depend on the affected brain region.

The literature describes that cerebrovascular diseases (CVD) are the third cause of death in the world, second only to heart diseases in general and cancer. Around 40 to 50% of individuals who suffer a stroke die during the first months that follow (ANDRÉ, 2006). According to Fukujima (2005), in Brazil, stroke is considered among the most cause of death in adults, and is also one of the most disabling diseases, with high rates of mortality, disability, and high social and economic cost.

Depression is the most frequent psychiatric complication of stroke. Post-stroke depression (PAVC), that is, that which occurs after the stroke, is associated with increased mortality, greater impairment in physical and language functioning, longer hospitalization, and reduced quality of life. Studies reveal that depression has been little considered in stroke patients, so much so that its diagnosis is made in 20% to 50% of cases. The etiology of CVAPD is multifactorial. Despite these data, the occurrence of CAPD has been associated with some risk factors, such as female gender, younger age, precarious social network, history of depressive disorder and

history of previous strokes, psychological factors resulting from damage caused by neurological sequelae, hormonal factors such as changes in the pituitary-hypothalamus-adrenal axis (HHA), neuropsychological deficits, and location of the stroke. When CVAPD is diagnosed and treated, there is an improvement in functional recovery and a reduction in cognitive impairment (TERRONI et al., 2009).

According to Paula (et al., 2008), more and more scientific studies developed to investigate the Central Nervous System (CNS) are considering, in addition to their neuroanatomical substrates, the cognitive and behavioral aspects dealt with by neuropsychology. In the specific case of stroke, cognitive and affective changes are frequent, both in the acute phase and in the rehabilitation period, making its investigation fundamental.

In clinical practice, neuropsychological techniques have contributed significantly to the treatment of the disease. Performs comparative and qualitative analysis of the results obtained, allowing a relationship between the patient's history, behavior, and neurological dysfunction; the correlation with the information coming from other exams and the patient's clinical condition. However, from a scientific point of view, it is still not known with clarity which cognitive functions are involved, which neuropsychological instruments are most indicated, which are the relationships between cognition and depression, or even between cognition and injury resulting from stroke (PAULA et al. ., 2008).

Neuropsychology studies cognitive, emotional, and personality disorders caused by brain damage. It is also called behavioral neurology because the brain expresses the injuries suffered in behavioral disorders. It has diagnostic, therapeutic, and cognitive objectives, enabling the raising of hypotheses about normal brain functioning (GIL, 2002).

Therefore, the neurocognitive assessment of patients after brain injury is important to complement the classic studies of aphasia with tests based on cognitive models of language. In turn, neuropsychological rehabilitation is necessary, given that Neuropsychology provides techniques that make it possible to treat the appropriate

changes (TOAZZA, 2010).

REVISION OF LITERATURE

Cerebral Vascular accidents (CVA) can cause cognitive and emotional damage to memory and language, visuospatial functions, executive functions, attention, and even mood swings. Regarding emotional aspects, depression seems to be the most prevalent disorder, depending on the location and laterality of the lesion, and the most evident behavioral changes occur in compulsive behavior, lack of inhibitory control, and obsessive-compulsive behavior (TERRONI, et al., 2003).

The first to note that people with the cerebrovascular disease were vulnerable to depression was Kraepelin (1901/1915), in which depression would be an understandable reaction to brain injury. A study published in the *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry* in 2009 reveals that the prevalence of post-stroke depression ranges from 23% to 60%. In addition, it suggests the fact that CVAPD is associated with worse prognosis and evolution, worsening of cognitive dysfunctions, and reduced quality of life, with stroke affecting the basal ganglia, left frontal region, and/or structures of the prefrontosubcortical circuit, and, it is related to the frequency and severity of CVAPD, that is, the study found that patients with depression had more frequent infarctions, affecting the prefrontosubcortical circuit or some of its structures: caudate, pallidum, genu of the internal capsule and anterior capsule, especially in the left hemisphere (TERRONI et al., 2009).

Another study, also published in the *Revista de Psiquiatria Clínica*, in 2010, reveals that post-stroke depression is an underdiagnosed condition since only about 30% of patients with this condition are diagnosed by physicians who are not psychiatrists. Several studies have demonstrated the therapeutic efficacy of antidepressants such as nortriptyline, fluoxetine, and citalopram in the treatment of post-stroke depression. However, the biggest current obstacle is not the treatment of this pathology, but its diagnosis (SOUZA et al., 2010).

In a case study, Reichelt & Fraga (2006) sought subsidies to substantiate the occurrence of post-stroke depression and its consequences in an

individual's life. It was observed that the results of the neuropsychological assessment pointed to depression, from the conduct of observations and interviews to the neuropsychological tests and tests. The losses found in the tests in the areas of memory and attention, which depend on the state of humor, added to the aspects of the conduct depression, informed by the family and by the patient, suggested a post-stroke depression, depicting in a framework on which a syndrome resulting from the interaction between functional and neurological factors is configured, where humor played a fundamental role, both in terms of what preceded ischemia as in the post-ischemia phase. In short, acting as cause and consequence (REICHELT & FRAGA, 2006).

Depression severity is also associated with functional and cognitive impairment in all domains. Generally, depending on the size of the lesion, the neuropsychological profile of patients with moderate and severe depressive symptoms may be affected, causing damage to memory, visual perception, and language domains (TERRONI et al., 2009).

The neuropsychocognitive assessment of post-brain injury patients is important to complete the classic studies of aphasias with tests based on cognitive models of language. Their results address not only the cognitive deficits caused by the neurological injury but also the skills preserved and possible strategies for rehabilitation. Not only do they help to better characterize the condition, but they also raise fundamental information for the therapeutic planning of cognitive rehabilitation. Despite the diffusion of international neurocognitive assessment instruments, Brazilian tests are still rare, justifying the importance of finding out how they are being performed nationally in post-stroke patients (TOAZZA, 2010).

The use of a neuropsychological battery enables a better analysis of the cognitive impairments in these patients (TERRONI, 2009). Impairments in cognition may be related to poor quality of life in the long term in ischemic strokes, among which, affect functions, the author Scheffer et al. (2013) points out:

[...] neuropsychological rehabilitation is necessary, considering that Neuropsychology provides techniques

that make it possible to treat the necessary alterations, which are extremely important and establishes which among the available tools are the most appropriate for the objective to be achieved in the context of cognitive and emotional rehabilitation (SCHEFFER et al., 2013 apud NOREÑA, 2010).

Cognitive rehabilitation is considered one of the components of neuropsychological rehabilitation. According to Fuentes (2008, p.399) cognitive rehabilitation “is a clinical area of interdisciplinary action that seeks both recovery and compensation for altered cognitive functions resulting from brain damage”. Among its functions, the rehabilitation neuropsychology encompasses a combination of psychotherapy, family participation through groups, and therapeutic instructions to patients, always being carried out within a multidisciplinary context.

For patients affected by stroke, the objectives of rehabilitation are: to prevent complications; recover as much of the brain functions compromised by the stroke as possible, which may be temporary or permanent; return the patient to social life, both in the family and at work, reintegrating him with the best possible quality of life (SCHEFFER et al., 2013 apud Damiani & Yokoo, 2002).

To Silva (2010, p.24) “Cognitive rehabilitation concentrates efforts to help patients understand their limitations and compensate or restore lost functions to improve adaptation and facilitate independence”. The Neuropsychologist will carry out an assessment to identify deficits and cognitive abilities, considering it within the individual’s personal and social context. This intervention may also involve caregiver education and support (SILVA, 2010).

In general, it can be said that the main objective of rehabilitation is the optimization of physical, vocational, and social functioning after an illness or neurological damage. Munõz and Ruiz (1999) propose as basic objectives of a neuropsychological rehabilitation program; 1) provide a model that helps the patient and his family to understand

what happened; 2) provide skills training strategies to recover and compensate for cognitive deficits, improve the patient’s performance in different social situations and help him to establish realistic work commitments and interpersonal relationships; 3) promote a realistic environment of hope. (CANCELA, 2008 apud Munõz and Ruiz, 1999).

Patients’ recovery targets the affected areas and recovery should start as soon as possible. In addition to the motor and cognitive consequences, which are direct consequences of the injury, there are psychological changes at an emotional level (anxiety and depression), discouragement, as well as self-reference variables, such as self-efficacy, self-concept, self-esteem, and social support, which will affect the patient’s commitment to recovery. The decrease in expectations due to the interaction of cognitive, and emotional variables is physical, reduces the patient’s motivation to commit to recovery, being more serious the more advanced the patient’s age is (PAIS RIBEIRO, 2005).

In the field of care, the literature reports on the low level of detection of CVADD and, consequently, a large number of patients who do not receive adequate treatment. Bearing in mind that the treatment is efficient, leading to remission of CVAPD and, in turn, improving the evolution and prognosis of patients regarding the recovery of losses resulting from the stroke. In terms of the high rate of depression, it suggests the need for monitoring and evaluation of programs that include interventions to treat depressive symptoms and AVCAD. The repercussions of stroke on individuals are many, and knowledge of factors associated with quality of life after stroke can provide valuable information on strategies that can be used by health professionals to improve outcomes in the treatment of patients with CVAPD (TERRONI, 2009).

The aforementioned author warns that in the sphere of scientific investigation, in general, there is great variation in methodology in the various areas of study of DPAVC. The possibility of replicating the studies is necessary to verify the evidence. The inclusion in studies of patients with depression before stroke brings characteristics and risk factors that interfere with the analysis of results. For example, instead of studying post-stroke depression, we would be studying recurrent depression

triggered by a stroke. Therefore, this is crucial for the analysis of the neuroanatomical correlates of CVAPD. Longitudinal studies are needed and may clarify the nature of the association between CVPD and neurocognitive changes (Ibid.).

CONCLUSIONS

The relationships between depression and stroke appear to be bidirectional and influenced by both emotional and neurological conditions. Although studies have not yet been able to clearly explain such relationships, research aimed at clarifying the pathophysiology of post-stroke depression remains in development and could bring valuable contributions to the treatment of these patients and the improvement of their quality of life (PAULA et al., 2008).

The author also reveals that studies of the neuropsychological aspects of this disease are of great importance, allowing various aspects studied in these patients, such as their personality and history, to come to identify possible risk factors for depression. And, it also, allows a better understanding of the critical state of post-stroke depression, paving the way for the search for more effective theories of diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of possible cognitive sequelae in patients. Thus, neuropsychology, in turn, has been improving in the development of techniques capable of identifying such dysfunctions and specific neuropsychological patterns in post-stroke depression (Ibidem).

According to Terroni (2003), a method that can also contribute to greater knowledge about the pathophysiology of post-stroke depression in future research is the investigation of neuroanatomical areas affected by the stroke as risk factors for post-stroke depression (TERRONI, et al. ., 2003).

Toazza (2010) warns of the reduced number of standardized and available Brazilian neuropsychological instruments, considering the few instruments validated in the country or produced for the Brazilian population. There is an urgent need for further research in this area to provide a more adequate survey of cognitive symptoms in the clinical population, especially post-stroke, precisely because it is the most frequent

cause of language disorders.

Therefore, the literature describes that CAPD is very frequent and underdiagnosed. Several risk factors are involved in the occurrence of CVAPD. The negative repercussions of depression in stroke patients are many and significant, as studies have pointed out. Improved knowledge about the factors involved in CVAPD can help improve efficient therapeutic intervention and increase diagnostic accuracy (TERRONI et al., 2009).

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